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Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

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Summary:

This is the first of ROMEO's e-newsletters. The e-newsletters will be released twice a year. This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created and sent and what makes up the mailing lists. The newsletter is then displayed.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
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Content

1. Creating and sending e-newsletters	4
2. Mailing list.....	4
3. Newsletter 1.....	4

1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to *MailPoet* and the *WordPress* Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically as emails. The software splits the mailing list and doesn't send the e-newsletter to more than 30 persons at a time so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Mailing list

We have created 3 mailing lists for the different communication purposes that we may have.

- List 1: all the persons working for ROMEIO within ROMEIO's partners;
- List 2: other people within ROMEIO's partners, not working directly on the project but who might be interested in the project
- List 3: other people not part of ROMEIO that partners want to inform about the project.

All 9 partners had the opportunity to send names for these three categories and we collected a total of 91 people.

ROMEIO's 1st e-newsletter was sent to all 3 mailing lists on Wednesday 30 March 2016.

3. Newsletter 1

Display problems? [View this newsletter in your browser.](#)

Welcome from ROMEIO's project coordinator

Welcome to the ROMEIO project and its first newsletter.

This is the first of a series of bi-annual newsletters aiming at providing you with updates on what happens with ROMEIO.

ROMEIO stands for Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation. The project started in September 2015 and has received 6 million euros funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The aim of ROMEIO is to **reduce energy consumption** by up to 80% **and emissions** by up to 90% in industrial catalytic gas-phase reactions.

If we succeed, it will be a small revolution for chemical process engineering and a huge step towards more sustainable processes.

...

Read the full editorial [here](#).

Website launch

On Thursday 28 January, the ROMEIO website was officially launched!

The website is available from the following URL: www.romeio-h2020.eu/

Please feel free to browse and contact us should you have any questions.

Partners

First-class research groups are working hand in hand with pioneering industrial companies to ensure this innovative reactor concept becomes a reality. There are 9 partners involved from all over Europe.

To find out more about our partners, their expertise and what they bring to the project, please visit the ROMEIO website, [partners page](#).

ROMEIO's brochure

This brochure provides the basic information on the ROMEIO project.

The brochure is available [here](#).

ROMEIO's kick-off and first progress meetings

ROMEIO's kick-off meeting took place on 22 September 2015 in Brussels, Belgium. During this meeting, the workplan was carefully detailed for everyone to find their bearings in this ambitious project. Read more about the kick-off meeting [here](#).

On 7 and 8 March 2016, the first progress meeting was held in Aachen, Germany, hosted by RWTH. The goal of this meeting was twofold: keep everyone updated on the latest developments and get some insights from the partners. Read more about the first progress meeting [here](#).

SPIRE projects event

A SPIRE projects event will take place on 20 April 2016 in Brussels. This event is public and will be followed by a 2-day workshop on the impact of collaborative research projects. This workshop is on invitation only.

SPIRE is a contractual Public-Private Partnership dedicated to innovation in resource and energy efficiency and enabled by the process industries.

The public event on 20 April will be a good opportunity to learn about the other SPIRE projects and to network with these.

Focus on Haris Kadrispahic

Haris is Head of Projects at LiqTech International, Denmark.

"I am Danish with Bosnian origin. I have a commercial background and not as many of my colleagues a technological background.

...

The ROMEO concept will reduce significantly energy intensity while also reducing the downstream processing steps. This has never been done before."

Read the full interview [here](#).

Focus on Morten Logemann

Morten is a PhD candidate at the RWTH Aachen University, Germany.

"I do like the diversity of being a PhD student. It is a lot about interacting with different types of people, getting to know project partners from huge companies, learning how to teach younger students and get insights in project management."

Read the full interview [here](#).

Focus on Martin Wiese

Martin is a PhD candidate at the RWTH Aachen University, Germany.

"I was born in Aachen and having one of the best universities for natural and engineering sciences in Germany here it was an easy choice for me to stay.

I studied mechanical engineering at the RWTH Aachen University as one of the last diploma students."

Read the full interview [here](#).

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